

Effect of inorganic phosphorus on algae excised from Inland Waters

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ABSTRACT

The present communication deals with the impact of inorganic phosphorus on composition and numeric strength of algae under standard test conditions. Samples of algae were excised from three inland water resources of Bhopal and were housed separately in three sets of microcosms. Different concentrations of phosphoric acid were added, in each set, to categorically assess the nutrient impact. Significant changes were observed in algal community in response to addition of inorganic phosphorus. Higher concentration of phosphorus created inhibitory effect on majority of microphytes, except a few viz. *Merismopedia punctata* and *Microcystis aeruginosa*.

INTRODUCTION

Cultural eutrophication of lentic habitats, has been a cause of global concern. Excessive mixing of nutrients, in the form of sewage and fertilizers creates a tangible risk to the down-hill body of water affecting its limnobiological components.

Retrospection of literature on microcosmal studies unravels a sheer paucity of data. Chu (1942) initiated experiments for evaluating the effect of nutrients on plankton. Similar studies were carried out by Brink (1965) and Fitzgerald (1969). Taylor *et. al.* (1990) correlated the effect of nutrient availability with algal growth potential (AGP) in a microcosm. In the present study an effort has been made to foresee the impact of external phosphorus loading on planktonic biota of three different water resources

of Bhopal viz. Upper lake (UL), Lower lake (LL) and Chunabhatti reservoir (CR).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Microcosms were set up in laboratory after Wetzel & Likens (1979) and Yasuno (1985). Four identical aquaria were established, for each lake, with lake water sediment and phytoplankton contained therein. Different concentrations of phosphoric acid (0.4 cc, 0.8 cc & 1.2 cc) were administered in three out of four aquaria and labelled as A, B & C respectively. The one, left untreated, was marked as controlled. Analysis of physico-chemical and biological parameters was done (after APHA, 1989) at an interval of 1, 3, 5, 10 and 15 days to record progressive changes in the limnobiology of treated water.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In microcosms, developed from natural lake waters, total phosphorus varied from 6.0 mg/l to 10.0 mg/l (UL), 4.5 mg/l to 9.2 mg/l (LL) and 4.8 mg/l to 7.3 mg/l (CR). The algal cells consumed more and more phosphorus and a competition among different algal groups was witnessed resulting in part elimination of Chlorophyceae and subsequent release of phosphorus.

Unlike total phosphorus the experimental waters indicated fractional utilization of orthophosphate by living biota unexceptionally in all conditions and its values ranged between 0.014 mg/l & 0.036 mg/l (UL). Lower lake water contained less amount of orthophosphate ranging from 0.012 mg/l to 0.035 mg/l. The orthophosphate contents in Chunabhatti reservoir were quite high extending from 0.021 mg/l to 0.04 mg/l in samples. Very high values ranging between 2.0 mg/l to 11.23 mg/l were recorded by Jacob (1993) after similar treatment.

Algal population gave varied response in microcosms. Chu (1941) found that different plankton had different requirements of phosphorus. They grew luxuriantly in a medium with phosphorus concentration between 1.0 mg/l & 7.0 mg/l but their growth was hindered at a concentration below 0.05 mg/l.

During present study, phytoplankton units fluctuated from 5,340 org/l to 12,240 org/l (UL), 9,600 org/l to 17,040 org/l (LL) and 8,300 org/l to 20,480 org/l (CR). In all treated microcosms phytoplankton population expressed reduction with respect to concentration and duration.

Chlorophyceae exhibited a phase of decreasing relative growth in all microcosms. Green algal count of lower lake water was somewhat higher than that of Upper lake and Chunabhatti reservoir. Induced nutrient at first, acted upon green algae which were most favoured in natural waters at that period. At lower dosage *i.e.*, 5 mg/l it sustained considerable floral density upto 15th day but higher concentration produced an inhibitory effect. Extrinsic stimuli of phosphorus (10 mg/l) seemed to have reached the upper limits of its stimulating range for chlorophytes and then became toxic when the cells had an opportunity to accumulate the nutrient. At the end of the experiment, the microcosms contained few individuals of *Crucigenia* sps. and *Scenedesmus* sps. As additional species, *Actinastrum hantzschii* (LL & CR), *Chlorella vulgaris* (CR) and *Eudorina elegans* (LL & CR) occurred rarely.

The condition of Bacillariophyceae was also frustrating. Upper & Lower lake water showed diatomic loss with periodicity (in all conditions). Greater amplification of Cyanophyceae and heavy suppression of filamentous green algae together with diatoms pointed out that higher phosphate concentration had inimical effect on this group. Diatoms of Chunabhatti reservoir responded exceptionally well under enriched condition and *Melosira granulata* proved to be a dominant taxon.

Under controlled condition, Cyanophyceae underwent a slow devastation in Upper lake water, since blue green algae require nutrient-rich conditions (Shapiro 1973). During high phosphorus loading myxophytes grew exponentially. A conspicuous spread of *Microcystis aeruginosa* and *Merismoyedia*

Table-1. Physico-chemical and biological response to addition of phosphoric acid

Parameters	Unit	Lake	Controlled		A-Microcosm		B-Microcosm		C-Microcosm	
			Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max
pH	—	UL	8.0	9.0	6.5	8.0	6.5	7.5	6.0	7.5
	—	LL	8.0	8.5	6.5	8.0	6.0	7.5	6.0	7.5
	—	CR	7.0	7.5	7.0	8.0	6.5	8.0	6.6	8.00
Total Phosphorus	mg/l	UL	6.0	6.8	7.2	8.5	7.6	9.0	8.2	10.0
		LL	4.5	5.0	4.5	6.6	5.9	8.0	6.8	9.2
		CR	4.8	5.9	4.9	6.1	6.0	6.5	6.8	7.3
Orthophosphate	mg/l x -10	UL	0.14	0.27	0.14	0.30	0.22	0.32	0.28	0.36
		LL	0.12	0.24	0.16	0.27	0.18	0.30	0.21	0.35
		CR	0.21	0.30	0.21	0.33	0.30	0.38	0.34	0.40
Total Phytoplankton	Org/l x 1000	UL	5.38	11.44	5.96	12.26	5.90	12.16	5.92	11.44
		LL	9.60	16.16	10.58	16.16	10.90	16.28	10.58	16.88
		CR	8.34	18.34	10.98	19.14	13.46	19.10	16.56	20.70

punctata was noticed in the treated microcosms of Lower lake and Chunabhatti reservoir. Stockner & Shortreed (1988) suggested the blue green algae grow effusively when phosphorus concentration in water exceeded 16.0 µg/l. Availing the competitive advantage over diatoms and green algae, these species formed a thin film on the surface of aquaria despite thermal minima. The system did not consider other factors like pH which can be held responsible for creating blooms.

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